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FRS 18 Adoption on Corporate Financial Reporting Practices in Nigeria

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ABSTRACT

This study examined the effect of IFRS 18 adoption on corporate financial reporting practices in Nigeria. The specific objectives were to evaluate how these IFRS 18 operating profit subtotals, classification of income and expenses, and disclosure of management-defined performance measures influenced the reliability of financial reporting in the Nigerian context. A cross-sectional survey design was adopted, which allowed the collection of data from professional accountants at a single point in time. The study population comprised 2,557 professional accountants in 74 accounting firms across South-East Nigeria, with a sample size of 346 determined using the Taro Yamane formula. Data were collected through structured electronic questionnaires, capturing respondents' perceptions of IFRS 18 presentation of operating profit subtotals, classifications of income and expenses into operating, investing, and financing activities and disclosure of management-defined performance measures on the reliability of financial reporting in Nigeria. Hypotheses were tested using ANOVA analysis. The findings revealed that IFRS 18 presentation of operating profit subtotals, shows positively and significantly affects the reliability of financial reporting ($\beta = 0.265$, $p = 0.000$), classification of income and expenses, and disclosure of management-defined performance measures all significantly enhanced the reliability of financial reporting in Nigeria has a coefficient of 0.216 and a p-value of 0.000, IFRS 18 disclosure of management-defined performance measures. The coefficient of 1.289 with a p-value of 0.000 indicates that a one-unit increase in MDPM disclosure leads to a 1.289-unit increase in the reliability of financial reporting. In conclusion, the adoption of IFRS 18 strengthened financial reporting by providing clearer structure, better categorization, and improved transparency, thereby supporting more reliable and decision-useful financial statements for stakeholders. Thus, based on the finding that IFRS 18 presentation of operating profit subtotals has a positive and significant effect on the reliability of financial reporting, it was recommended that corporate accountants and financial reporting teams in Nigerian companies ensure consistent application of the standardized operating profit subtotals in all financial statements. financial controllers and internal auditors within firms should actively implement and monitor compliance with the classification requirements. By doing so, companies can maintain uniformity and transparency in reporting, reduce inconsistencies, and allow management and external users to make better-informed decisions based on a clear breakdown of operational, investment, and financing activities. company executives and board finance committees provide detailed, accurate, and standardized disclosure of management-defined performance metrics in their financial reports. This will enhance transparency, reduce the risk of misleading reporting, and enable investors, analysts, and regulators to better evaluate management's performance and the company's true financial health.

Keywords: IFRS 18 adoption, corporate financial reporting practices, operating profit sub-totals, classification of income and expenses

1.0 INTRODUCTION

The global business environment has undergone profound changes in recent decades, driven by increasing globalization, technological advancements, and heightened investor expectations. Firms today operate in a highly interconnected and competitive landscape where the accuracy, transparency, and comparability of

financial information are paramount (Lawal et al., 2025). In Nigeria, as in many emerging markets, corporate financial reporting plays a critical role in enabling investors, regulators, and other stakeholders to make informed decisions. Over the years, inconsistencies in reporting practices, differing accounting standards, and inadequate disclosure have posed challenges for evaluating firm performance and ensuring accountability (Zahid et al., 2025; Cheng, 2024). These issues have highlighted the need for globally recognized accounting frameworks that provide uniformity in reporting practices. International Financial Reporting Standards (IFRS) have been widely adopted worldwide to harmonize financial reporting and reduce discrepancies between national standards (Kumawat & Sodha, 2024; Ibem et al., 2024; Ame & Agoh, 2021). Specifically, IFRS 18, which supersedes IAS 1, seeks to standardize the presentation of financial statements, focusing on enhancing transparency, comparability, and the decision-usefulness of reported information (Tulokas, 2025). By offering a structured approach to presenting operating profit, disaggregating income and expenses, and defining management-defined performance measures, IFRS 18 provides a benchmark for consistent reporting. In Nigeria, where financial markets are growing and attracting both domestic and foreign investor, the adoption of IFRS 18 represents a major step toward aligning local corporate reporting with international best practices. Understanding the broader context of this adoption is essential to appreciating its potential implications for corporate governance, investor confidence, and the overall financial ecosystem.

The adoption of IFRS 18 is particularly relevant in today's business environment due to its potential to influence corporate financial reporting practices and the quality of information available to stakeholders (Samuel et al., 2024). Modern investors demand timely, accurate, and comparable financial data to assess the performance and sustainability of firms before committing capital. Derdoubia and Rahmani (2025) argued that IFRS 18 addresses these demands by prescribing the presentation and disclosure of financial statements in a way that improves clarity and uniformity. For instance, the standard requires the classification of income and expenses into operating, investing, and financing activities, and it mandates the disclosure of management-defined performance indicators. These requirements help ensure that financial statements provide a true and fair view of an organization's financial position and performance. In Nigeria, where financial reporting practices have historically faced challenges related to inconsistent disclosures and limited comparability, IFRS 18 offers a framework for strengthening corporate transparency and accountability. Additionally, the adoption of IFRS 18 can influence investor perception by enhancing confidence in the reported figures, thereby facilitating better decision-making in capital markets. By standardizing reporting practices, IFRS 18 can reduce information asymmetry, minimize the risk of earnings manipulation, and promote more reliable evaluation of corporate performance (Czajor, 2024). The relevance of IFRS 18 extends beyond compliance, as it also supports strategic financial management, enabling companies to communicate performance effectively to shareholders and regulators, and ultimately contributing to the growth of Nigeria's financial markets.

IFRS 18 adoption has a direct impact on corporate financial reporting practices by reshaping the way financial information is prepared, presented, and interpreted (Samuel et al., 2024). One of the primary effects of the standard is the establishment of structured reporting formats, which enhances consistency across firms and industries. By requiring firms to present operating profit as a distinct subtotal and to classify income and expenses according to their nature, IFRS 18 reduces the variability in reporting approaches that previously made comparisons across companies difficult (Lee, 2024). The standard also emphasizes transparency through the disclosure of management-defined performance measures, which allows stakeholders to better understand the assumptions and metrics that managers use to assess performance. For Nigerian firms, these changes imply a shift from traditional, locally driven accounting practices toward internationally recognized norms, necessitating adjustments in accounting policies, internal control systems, and financial statement preparation processes.

In an effective corporate financial reporting environment, companies provide accurate, transparent, and comparable financial statements that allow investors, regulators, and other stakeholders to make informed decisions (Ibem et al., 2024). Firms clearly distinguish between operating, investing, and financing activities in their reports, while subtotals such as operating profit and management-defined performance

measures are consistently presented. Such reporting practices enhance accountability and foster trust in the financial system, enabling shareholders to evaluate firm performance reliably and facilitating the smooth allocation of resources in the capital market (Samuel et al., 2024). In this context, the quality and clarity of financial reporting serve as a critical foundation for sustainable business growth and investor confidence. In practice, however, many firms have struggled to achieve consistent and transparent financial reporting. Subtotals like operating profit are sometimes omitted, and management-defined performance measures are not always fully disclosed. These reporting gaps make it difficult for stakeholders to compare financial information across companies, assess performance accurately, and evaluate the financial health of firms.

These gaps in reporting practices can have significant consequences for the Nigerian business environment. Investors may make decisions based on incomplete or misleading information, thus increasing the risk of poor investment outcomes and capital misallocation. Regulators and policymakers may find it challenging to monitor corporate performance and enforce compliance effectively. Additionally, inconsistent reporting can undermine public confidence in the financial market, discourage foreign investment, and hinder the growth of domestic capital markets. Without clear and comparable financial statements, the ability of firms to attract investment, demonstrate accountability, and maintain sustainable operations may be compromised. Although IFRS 18 adoption has been studied internationally, gaps exist regarding its impact on corporate financial reporting in Nigeria. Tulokas (2025) and Derdouba and Rahmani (2025) focused on global presentation and disclosure requirements, while Samuel et al. (2024) and Lee (2024) analyzed performance reporting. Czajor (2024) and Castro (2024) highlighted transparency and implementation issues outside Nigeria. Cheng (2024) and Kumawat and Sodha (2024) studied global and Indian firms, whereas Ibem et al. (2024) and Ame and Agoh (2021) focused on Nigerian banks. Limited research exists on Nigerian firms, especially on operating profit subtotals, income classification, and management-defined performance measures. To address this gap, this study is to assess the effect of IFRS 18 adoption on corporate financial reporting practices in Nigeria. The specific objectives are as follows:

1. To evaluate how IFRS 18 presentation of operating profit subtotals affects the reliability of financial reporting in Nigeria.
2. To examine the degree to which IFRS 18 classifications of income and expenses into operating, investing, and financing activities affects the reliability of financial reporting in Nigeria.
3. To assess the effect of IFRS 18 disclosure of management-defined performance measures on the reliability of financial reporting in Nigeria.

2.0 Review of Related Literature

Conceptual Review

IFRS 18

The International Accounting Standards Board (IASB) issued IFRS 18 – Presentation and Disclosure in Financial Statements in April 2024 to replace IAS 1 (Presentation of Financial Statements). IFRS 18 aims to improve comparability, transparency, and consistency in how entities present and disclose financial performance information, particularly in the statement of profit or loss. The standard responds to long-standing concerns by investors and other users regarding inconsistent performance measures and limited comparability across firms and industries

The standard provides a framework for how entities should report their financial performance and position, focusing on enhancing transparency, comparability, and usefulness of financial information for decision-making. Tulokas (2025) noted that IFRS 18 mandates the classification of income and expenses into operating, investing, and financing activities, and requires clear disclosure of management-defined performance measures, allowing users of financial statements to better understand the financial outcomes of the organization. This standard replaces previous requirements such as IAS 1 and introduces new presentation subtotals and categories to align reporting with users' expectations for relevant, decision-useful information (Derdouba & Rahmani, 2025).

The standard emphasizes providing a structured approach to reporting financial performance that enables stakeholders to assess the organization's ability to generate cash flows, manage resources, and achieve sustainable returns. It seeks to limit inconsistencies in financial reporting across firms and industries by introducing standardized rules for presenting operating profit and other key financial aggregates (Lee, 2024). By requiring the disclosure of alternative performance measures, IFRS 18 reduces the potential for misleading information while increasing the comparability of financial statements between entities operating in similar contexts (Czajor, 2024).

IFRS 18 also aims to improve the interpretability of financial reports for investors, creditors, regulators, and other stakeholders (Samuel et al., 2024). It establishes principles that guide firms in presenting financial outcomes in ways that facilitate an understanding of their operational efficiency, investment strategies, and financing structures. By doing so, the standard enhances confidence in financial statements, allowing stakeholders to make more informed decisions about resource allocation and strategic planning (Castro, 2024). Its adoption reflects a shift towards harmonization in global accounting practices and strengthens the credibility of reported financial data, providing a consistent basis for assessing corporate performance. Through IFRS 18, organizations are required to ensure that their financial reporting practices reflect both internal management objectives and external regulatory expectations (Czajor, 2024). The focus on structured presentation, detailed disclosure, and the inclusion of management-defined measures ensures that financial statements communicate a true reflection of organizational performance. This standard serves as a benchmark for financial reporting quality, establishing expectations for transparency, accountability, and clarity in reporting practices across various industries and jurisdictions.

Recent Changes Introduced by IFRS 18

IFRS 18 has introduced several notable changes aimed at enhancing the transparency and comparability of financial statements (Samuel et al., 2024). One of the most significant adjustments is the requirement for the presentation of operating profit as a separate subtotal in the income statement. Previously, financial statements often combined operating and non-operating items, making it difficult for users to assess a firm's operational efficiency (Tulokas, 2025). By mandating this subtotal, IFRS 18 provides a clearer distinction between core business operations and ancillary activities, allowing stakeholders to evaluate the sustainability and quality of earnings more accurately (Derdouba & Rahmani, 2025).

Another key change under IFRS 18 is the structured classification of income and expenses into operating, investing, and financing categories (Samuel et al., 2024). This categorization replaces prior flexible arrangements that allowed entities to present items according to their discretion. The new requirement ensures consistency across reporting entities, making it easier for investors and analysts to compare financial performance across firms and industries. It also helps in evaluating cash flow generation, investment strategies, and financial obligations, as each category reflects specific aspects of a company's operations and financing decisions (Lee, 2024).

IFRS 18 Presentation of Operating Profit Subtotals

The presentation of operating profit subtotals under IFRS 18 represents a significant advancement in financial reporting. By clearly defining operating activities and mandating consistent subtotals, the standard enhances comparability, transparency, and the decision usefulness of financial statements. Consequently, IFRS 18 strengthens operating profit as a key indicator of firm performance for investors, regulators, and academic researchers. IFRS 18 introduces defined categories for classifying income and expenses. Items classified as operating activities are presented above the operating profit subtotal and generally include revenue from principal operations, cost of sales, administrative and selling expenses, research and development costs, and other income and expenses arising from routine business activities. This classification ensures that operating profit reflects outcomes directly linked to the entity's value-creating processes (Derdouba & Rahmani, 2025).

The operating profit subtotal introduced by IFRS 18 has important implications for empirical research on firm performance, growth, and value creation. For comparative studies involving firms across

jurisdictions—such as Nigeria and South Africa—the standardised presentation of operating profit enhances cross-country comparability and improves the validity of empirical findings.

IFRS 18 Classification of Income and Expenses into Operating, Investing, and Financing Activities.

The International Accounting Standards Board (IASB) issued IFRS 18 – Presentation and Disclosure in Financial Statements to enhance the transparency, consistency, and comparability of financial performance reporting. A key innovation of IFRS 18 is the mandatory classification of income and expenses in the statement of profit or loss into operating, investing, and financing activities. This classification addresses deficiencies under IAS 1, where entities exercised considerable discretion, resulting in inconsistent presentation of financial performance across firms and jurisdictions. Under IFRS 18, operating activities comprise income and expenses arising from the entity's main business operations and other activities that do not meet the definition of investing or financing activities. Operating activities represent the entity's primary revenue-generating processes and form the basis for assessing core operating performance (Tulokas, 2025).

Investing activities under IFRS 18 relate to income and expenses arising from investments in assets that are expected to generate returns independently of the entity's main operations. These activities are generally associated with the acquisition, disposal, or holding of assets that are not integral to the entity's core operating cycle. The classification of income and expenses into operating, investing, and financing activities under IFRS 18 represents a major improvement in financial statement presentation. By aligning financial performance reporting with business activities while enforcing consistent classification rules, IFRS 18 enhances comparability, transparency, and the overall decision usefulness of financial statements for investors, regulators, and academic researchers.

IFRS 18 Disclosure of Management-Defined Performance Measures and Reliability

The introduction of IFRS 18 – Presentation and Disclosure in Financial Statements represents a significant regulatory development aimed at improving the quality of financial performance reporting. One of the most notable innovations of the standard is the formal regulation of Management-Defined Performance Measures (MDPMs). Prior to IFRS 18, such measures were widely used by management in external communications without consistent disclosure requirements, raising concerns regarding their reliability, neutrality, and potential for bias. IFRS 18 addresses these concerns by imposing structured disclosure requirements intended to enhance the reliability of performance information. Reliability in financial reporting is closely associated with faithful representation, which requires information to be complete, neutral, and free from material error. By requiring reconciliations to IFRS-defined measures and explanations of adjustments, IFRS 18 enhances the completeness and neutrality of management-defined performance measures, thereby strengthening faithful representation.

The disclosure of management-defined performance measures under IFRS 18 represents a major advancement in enhancing the reliability of financial reporting. By mandating transparent definitions, reconciliations, and consistent application of these measures, IFRS 18 reduces information asymmetry, limits managerial discretion, and strengthens the credibility of performance information. Consequently, the standard contributes significantly to improving the overall quality and reliability of financial statements (Ibem et al., 2024).

IFRS 18 also emphasizes enhanced disclosures for management-defined performance measures (Samuel et al., 2024). Companies are now required to provide detailed explanations of these measures, including how they are calculated, their rationale, and their relationship to the financial performance of the firm. This change aims to reduce the use of alternative performance measures that could mislead stakeholders. By formalizing the presentation and disclosure of such metrics, the standard enhances accountability and ensures that investors have access to relevant and reliable information for decision-making. Lastly, IFRS 18 introduces clearer guidelines for the aggregation and disaggregation of line items in financial statements (Tulokas, 2025). It requires firms to group similar items together while maintaining transparency about material components of each category. This structured approach improves the readability and comparability of statements, reducing ambiguity and enhancing the quality of reporting. Collectively, these changes ensure that financial statements prepared under IFRS 18 provide more

meaningful, decision-useful, and comparable information to users, strengthening confidence in corporate reporting practices.

Corporate Financial Reporting Practices

Corporate financial reporting practices refer to the procedures, methods, and approaches employed by companies to communicate their financial performance, position, and cash flows to internal and external stakeholders (Edwards, 2018). These practices involve the preparation and presentation of financial statements, such as the statement of financial position, income statement, statement of cash flows, and statement of changes in equity. They also encompass the selection and application of accounting policies, recognition and measurement of transactions, and adherence to applicable accounting standards, regulations, and frameworks. Corporate financial reporting practices ensure that information conveyed to stakeholders is reliable, consistent, and comparable over time, enabling effective decision-making and evaluation of the organization's financial health (Ali & Ahmed, 2007).

The practices extend beyond mere compliance, reflecting the quality, timeliness, and transparency of reporting. Firms employ various reporting strategies to provide an accurate account of their operations, including detailed disclosures, narrative explanations, and supplementary notes to the financial statements (Kapellas & Siougle, 2017). Financial reporting practices serve as the primary mechanism through which companies convey their financial performance and stewardship of resources, facilitating trust and accountability with shareholders, regulators, creditors, and potential investors. Through these practices, stakeholders gain insight into an organization's liquidity, profitability, solvency, and operational efficiency, which are critical for investment decisions, regulatory assessments, and strategic planning.

Vickneswaran (2025) argued that corporate financial reporting practices are influenced by both internal management priorities and external regulatory environments. Companies design their reporting processes to meet the expectations of auditors, regulatory authorities, and investors while ensuring that their financial information remains accurate and verifiable. Adopting established standards and guidelines, such as IFRS, allows organizations to maintain consistency in financial reporting, enabling comparisons across periods and with other entities in similar sectors (Ame & Agoh, 2021). These practices foster transparency in business operations, limit information asymmetry, and support informed decision-making. Through rigorous financial reporting practices, organizations communicate not only past performance but also provide a framework for evaluating future prospects. Accurate reporting demonstrates managerial competence, supports strategic planning, and strengthens stakeholder confidence. Corporate financial reporting practices encompass both the technical preparation of financial statements and the ethical responsibility to present information fairly, reflecting the organization's accountability to its stakeholders (Ibem et al., 2024). Effective reporting practices underpin the financial integrity of the organization, enhancing credibility and fostering sustainable relationships with the wider business environment. For the purpose of the study, reliability of financial reporting refers to the degree to which financial statements provide accurate, complete, and trustworthy information that users can depend on for decision-making (Okezie & Egeolu, 2019). It ensures that reported figures fairly represent a company's financial position and performance without bias or misstatement. Reliable financial reporting increases stakeholders' confidence, enabling investors, regulators, and management to make informed economic and strategic decisions (Olaoye et al., 2019).

Theoretical Framework

This study is anchored on Positive Accounting Theory (PAT) which was first propounded by Watts and Zimmerman in 1978 as a framework to explain and predict accounting practices rather than prescribe them (Dodor, 2024). Unlike normative accounting theories that suggest what accounting policies firms should adopt, PAT focuses on describing and understanding why firms choose certain accounting methods in practice (Stefan-Duicu & Sudacevski, 2024). The theory emerged from the recognition that accounting choices are influenced by economic and contractual incentives, regulatory requirements, and managerial decision-making, providing a foundation for explaining real-world accounting behavior. Over

the years, it has become one of the most influential theories in accounting research, particularly in understanding the motivations behind firms' reporting practices.

The main postulations of Positive Accounting Theory include the idea that managers make accounting policy choices to maximize their own wealth or to achieve specific economic objectives (Syehabudin, 2024). PAT identifies three key hypotheses: the bonus plan hypothesis, which suggests that managers on performance-based compensation plans will select accounting methods that increase reported income; the debt-equity hypothesis, which posits that firms with higher debt levels will choose accounting policies that reduce the likelihood of violating debt covenants; and the political cost hypothesis, which argues that larger firms are likely to adopt accounting methods that reduce reported profits to minimize political scrutiny. The theory emphasizes that accounting practices are driven by economic incentives and the contractual environment rather than by abstract notions of "best practices" or ethics (Stefan-Duicu & Sudacevski, 2024).

The relevance of Positive Accounting Theory to this study lies in its ability to explain how the adoption of IFRS 18 influences corporate financial reporting practices in Nigeria. By providing a framework for understanding managerial motivations in selecting accounting treatments and disclosing financial information, PAT helps illuminate why firms may adopt IFRS 18 standards to improve transparency, meet regulatory requirements, and signal reliability to investors. The theory also aids in analyzing how firms' economic incentives and reporting environments shape compliance with IFRS 18, particularly in areas such as the presentation of operating profit subtotals, classification of income and expenses, and disclosure of management-defined performance measures, thereby linking accounting policy choices directly to observed financial reporting outcomes.

Empirical Review

The study by Tulokas (2025) investigated the forthcoming International Accounting Standards Board (IASB) standard, IFRS 18, which is scheduled to replace IAS 1 beginning January 1, 2027, and assessed how its provisions addressed the information needs of investors. The research focused on understanding how the new standard reshaped mandatory financial disclosures and the degree to which these revisions enhanced the clarity and comparability of firms' financial statements. To achieve this aim, the author conducted an extensive review of academic literature and IASB documentation. Central themes included the relevance of operating profit and EBITDA as intermediate performance indicators, the increasing importance of disaggregation in financial reporting, and the role played by alternative performance measures in enhancing or distorting users' understanding. These hints were then evaluated against IFRS 18's major innovations, which introduced a mandatory operating profit subtotal, required companies to classify income and expenses into operating, investing, and financing categories, strengthened principles for aggregating and breaking down financial information, and imposed new disclosure obligations for management-defined performance measures. The study concluded that these structured subtotals and classification rules were likely to promote stronger comparability across firms and align more closely with investor demand for decision-useful metrics. The mandatory operating profit subtotal, in particular, supported prior evidence suggesting its superior ability to predict future returns relative to other profit measures. Furthermore, the clearer disaggregation guidelines and the formalized rules governing management-defined performance measures were expected to increase transparency and reduce the scope for opportunistic reporting.

Derdouba and Rahmani (2025) examined the presentation and disclosure requirements introduced under IFRS 18 and evaluated how these requirements affected other existing IFRS standards. Their study revealed that the new presentation and disclosure provisions significantly enhanced the overall quality of financial statements, enabling financial statement users to access more coherent and decision-relevant information. Based on these findings, the authors emphasized the importance of encouraging entities to prepare early for the transition to IFRS 18 to ensure a smoother implementation process.

Samuel et al. (2024) explored the broader implications of IFRS 18 on financial reporting. Their work highlighted that the standard would help firms communicate performance information that enabled users to assess future cash flow prospects and evaluate management's effectiveness in utilizing financial

resources. Since IFRS 18 marked the culmination of a major standard-setting effort on financial statement presentation, it represented a significant shift for IFRS-compliant entities. By replacing IAS 1 as the principal source of presentation requirements, IFRS 18 was expected to increase the comparability, understandability, and transparency of financial statements, thereby offering users a more faithful representation of a firm's financial position and performance. Companies will also need to disclose management-defined performance measure in the notes to the financial statement.

Lee (2024) conducted an empirical investigation into the establishment of IFRS 18 and its implications for financial reporting. Using data from 31 countries, including the United States and several European nations, covering the period from 1997 to 2019, the study found that the comprehensive presentation of operating profit using the residual category approach fostered a more conservative portrayal of operating performance and effectively constrained managerial discretion in classifying items as operating or non-operating. However, the study also suggested that this approach might weaken the persistence and value relevance of reported operating profit, thus limiting its usefulness to investors. To address these concerns, the study proposed that the introduction of a separate subtotal for ordinary operating profit, built on extraordinary income disclosures contained in the footnotes, could strengthen the usefulness of operating performance measures. The research also argued that policymakers in Korea needed to evaluate the implications of the revised definition of operating profit within the national regulatory environment and prepare adequately for its adoption.

Czajor (2024) assessed the contribution of IFRS 18 to improving the relevance and usefulness of financial statements for various stakeholders. The study adopted desk research, drawing upon academic literature, professional reports, accounting standards, and financial statements. Both inductive and deductive reasoning were applied to analyze the changes introduced by IFRS 18. The findings showed that the revised structure of IFRS-based financial statements was designed to enhance value for investors and improve the quality of performance reporting. IFRS 18 introduced additional mandatory subtotals in the income statement and required disclosure of management-defined performance measures. However, it did not explicitly define widely-used non-GAAP metrics. Despite this omission, the study argued that IFRS 18 could still promote greater transparency by reducing unnecessary supplementary disclosures and improving the quality of reported financial results.

Castro (2024) focused on the difficulties and prospects facing Brazilian companies in implementing IFRS 18. The study examined four main areas: proposed changes under the new standard, anticipated challenges and opportunities, legal barriers, and the practicality of meeting the implementation timeline. The analysis showed that while IFRS 18 offered opportunities for Brazilian firms to enhance their alignment with international reporting practices, it also posed significant complexity due to the required adjustments in presentation and disclosure. Legal conflicts with the Lei das S.A. (Brazilian Corporation Law) represented a major obstacle and would require legislative modification or regulatory relief to ensure conformity. The study also noted that many Brazilian companies relied heavily on outsourced accounting services, making coordinated implementation more difficult. To mitigate these risks, the study recommended early planning, capacity building, and close collaboration with legal experts to support a smoother transition.

Cheng (2024) examined the impact of International Financial Reporting Standards more broadly on global corporate accounting practices. By analyzing how IFRS had been implemented across countries, the study evaluated its role in standardizing financial reporting and influencing cross-border comparability. The findings indicated that the adoption of IFRS contributed significantly to greater transparency in financial information and provided a more consistent and reliable foundation for global investors to assess corporate performance.

Kumawat and Sodha (2024) analyzed how IFRS adoption affected financial reporting among large-cap consumer durables firms in India. Their descriptive study assessed a ten-year period from 2011–12 to 2020–21 using secondary data obtained from company financial reports. Analytical tools such as paired t-tests, Jamovi, Python, and Excel were used. The results showed that IFRS adoption enhanced reporting quality, particularly in relevance, faithful representation, and understandability. Firms such as Asian

Paints, Berger Paints, and Havells India exhibited consistent improvements in reporting quality after IFRS adoption. Nonetheless, the study noted persistent challenges in comparability, verifiability, and understandability, suggesting areas where reporting practices could still improve.

Ibem et al. (2024) evaluated how the implementation of IFRS affected the quality of financial reporting among commercial banks listed on the Nigerian Exchange Group. The research adopted an ex-post facto design and analyzed data from ten banks over two periods: the pre-IFRS era (2005–2011) and the post-IFRS era (2015–2021). Using paired t-tests, the study found a significant difference in value relevance, as measured by the book value of shares, before and after IFRS implementation. However, earnings management and timely loss recognition did not exhibit significant differences. These findings suggested that while IFRS enhanced certain aspects of reporting quality, other dimensions remained largely unchanged.

Ame and Agoh (2021) investigated how IFRS-related disclosures influenced financial reporting quality among listed deposit money banks in Nigeria. Using panel data covering eight years and employing a census of all 15 listed banks, the study found that disclosure of financial position had a significant positive effect on reporting quality. In contrast, disclosure of comprehensive income showed an insignificant positive relationship with reporting quality. The authors concluded that strong adherence to IFRS requirements remained essential for improving the quality of financial reports among Nigerian banks and recommended that institutions continue to comply fully with IFRS disclosure obligations.

3.0 METHODOLOGY

This study adopted a cross-sectional survey design to assess the impact of IFRS 18 adoption on corporate financial reporting practices in Nigeria. A cross-sectional design is appropriate because it allows the researcher to gather data from respondents at a single point in time, particularly those involved in preparing, auditing, or regulating financial statements under the IFRS framework (Nworie & Odah, 2024). This design also supports quantitative analysis, enabling the study to measure how IFRS 18 presentation of operating profit subtotals, classification of income and expenses, and disclosure of management-defined performance measures influence the reliability of financial reporting in Nigeria. The population of the study consists of 2,557 professional accountants working in 74 accounting firms across the South-East geopolitical zone of Nigeria. These professionals hold active practice licenses from either ICAN or ANAN and are regularly involved in preparing or auditing financial statements. Their experience with IFRS-based reporting makes them suitable respondents for assessing the perceived impact of IFRS 18 adoption on reporting reliability. The distribution of respondents is shown in Table 3.1.

Table 3.1: Population of the Study

State	ICAN	ANAN	Total Number of Professional Accountants in Practice
Anambra	9 accounting firms with 743 professional accountants	10 accounting firms with 229 professional accountants	972 professional accountants
Abia	4 accounting firms with 253 professional accountants	2 accounting firms with 41 professional accountants	294 professional accountants
Enugu	23 accounting firms with 492 professional accountants	9 accounting firms with 300 professional accountants	792 professional accountants
Imo	2 accounting firms with 48 professional accountants	7 accounting firms with 200 professional accountants	248 professional accountants
Ebonyi	2 accounting firms with 101 professional accountants	6 accounting firms with 150 professional accountants	251 professional accountants
Total			2,557 accountants

Source: Field Survey (2025)

The Taro Yamane formula was used to determine the sample size:

$$n = \frac{N}{1 + N(e)^2}$$

Where:

$$N = 2,557$$

$$e = 0.05$$

n = Sample size

$$n = \frac{2557}{1 + 2557(0.05)^2}$$

$$n = 345.89$$

Thus, 346 respondents formed the sample size of the study.

Data were collected using a structured, self-administered electronic questionnaire. This instrument was chosen because it allows efficient collection of standardized responses from a large number of professionals. The questionnaire items measured perceptions of IFRS 18's effect on reporting reliability, focusing on

- a. operating profit subtotals,
- b. classification of income/expenses into operating, investing, and financing activities,
- c. disclosure of management-defined performance measures.

A five-point Likert scale (1 = Strongly Disagree to 5 = Strongly Agree) was used. To ensure validity, the questionnaire was reviewed by experts in financial reporting and IFRS implementation. Content validity was confirmed by assessing the alignment of questionnaire items with IFRS 18 requirements and the study's objectives. The supervisor also evaluated face validity to ensure clarity, relevance, and appropriateness of all items. A pilot test was conducted using a small sample of professional accountants outside the main study population. Reliability was assessed using Cronbach's alpha to determine internal consistency of the items measuring IFRS 18 constructs. A coefficient of 0.70 and above was considered acceptable, confirming the reliability of the instrument.

Data were analyzed using the Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) version 25. Descriptive statistics (means, standard deviations, and percentages) were used to summarize responses. Given that the dependent variable (reliability of financial reporting) is assessed using ordered categorical responses, the study employed ANOVA analysis to test the three hypotheses.

The study specifies three ordinal regression models corresponding to the specific objectives:

$$RFR_i = a + b_1OPS_i + b_2CLF_i + b_3MDP_i + e_i \text{-----} eqi$$

Where:

RFR = Reliability of Financial Reporting

OPS = Presentation of Operating Profit Subtotals

CLF = Classification of Income and Expenses

MDP = Disclosure of Management-Defined Performance Measures

a = Constant

b = Coefficients

e = Error Term

Hypotheses were tested at the 5% level of significance. Thus, if $p \leq 0.05$, the null hypothesis was rejected, indicating that IFRS 18 significantly affects the reliability of financial reporting. However, if $p > 0.05$, the null hypothesis was accepted, indicating no significant effect.

4.0 DATA ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION

Descriptive Analysis

The questionnaire captured questions focused on the effect of IFRS 18 adoption on corporate financial reporting practices in Nigeria, specifically addressing the presentation of operating profit subtotals, classification of income and expenses into operating, investing, and financing activities, and disclosure of management-defined performance measures. The response key and assigned ranks were: Strongly Agree

(SA) – 5, Agree (A) – 4, Undecided (U) – 3, Disagree (D) – 2, and Strongly Disagree (SD) – 1. A response rate of about 76% was received as only 262 respondents participated as against the expected 346 sample size.

Table 4.1 Descriptive Statistics

S/N	IFRS 18 Presentation of Operating Profit Subtotals (OPS)	SD	D	U	A	SA	Mean
1	IFRS 18 operating profit subtotals improve clarity in financial statement presentation.	10	14	40	122	76	3.92
2	The revised operating profit structure enhances comparability across reporting entities.	32	58	30	95	47	3.26
3	Presenting standardized operating profit subtotals reduces ambiguity in performance reporting.	42	64	67	71	18	2.84
4	IFRS 18 operating profit requirements increase users' confidence in reported performance.	42	64	34	78	44	3.07
	IFRS 18 Classification of Income and Expenses (CIE)	SD	D	U	A	SA	Mean
5	Classifying income and expenses into operating, investing, and financing activities enhances transparency.	74	120	29	27	12	2.17
6	The new classification rules reduce inconsistencies in reporting financial performance.	88	69	71	28	6	2.22
7	IFRS 18 classification requirements help users better understand a company's core operations.	77	104	29	38	14	2.27
8	The classification framework improves comparability of financial statements across industries.	78	101	32	37	14	2.27
	IFRS 18 Disclosure of Management-Defined Performance Measures (MDPM)	SD	D	U	A	SA	Mean
9	Disclosing management-defined performance measures enhances financial statement transparency.	15	42	21	108	76	3.72
10	IFRS 18 MDPM disclosure rules reduce the risk of misleading performance reporting.	49	61	48	53	51	2.98
11	Increased MDPM disclosure provides users with better hints into management's view of performance.	41	91	32	32	66	2.97
12	Standardized MDPM requirements improve comparability across reporting entities.	40	61	34	68	59	3.17
	Reliability of Financial Reporting (RFR)	SD	D	U	A	SA	Mean
13	IFRS 18 enhances the reliability of corporate financial reporting in Nigeria.	46	62	47	49	58	3.04
14	Financial statements prepared under IFRS 18 are more credible to users.	34	94	32	57	45	2.94
15	IFRS 18 reduces subjectivity in the presentation and classification of financial information.	46	60	46	57	53	3.04
16	The adoption of IFRS 18 improves the overall quality and reliability of reported financial performance.	40	90	32	29	71	3.00

Source: Field Survey (2025)

The data presented in Table 4.1 provide a detailed view of respondents' perceptions regarding the impact of IFRS 18 adoption on corporate financial reporting practices in Nigeria. For the presentation of operating profit subtotals, the first item indicates that most respondents recognized the improvement in clarity in financial statements, with 122 agreeing and 76 strongly agreeing, resulting in a relatively high mean of 3.92. Conversely, when asked whether the revised operating profit structure enhances comparability across reporting entities, the responses were more dispersed, as 32 strongly disagreed and 58 disagreed, while 95 agreed and 47 strongly agreed, producing a mean of 3.26, reflecting moderate agreement. The third item, which explored whether standardized operating profit subtotals reduce ambiguity in performance reporting, showed a larger proportion of disagreement, with 42 strongly disagreeing and 64 disagreeing, alongside 71 agreeing and only 18 strongly agreeing, giving a lower

mean of 2.84. For the fourth item, concerning the confidence users place in reported performance, responses were somewhat mixed, with 42 strongly disagreeing, 64 disagreeing, 78 agreeing, and 44 strongly agreeing, resulting in a mean of 3.07.

For the classification of income and expenses into operating, investing, and financing activities, the responses reflect some skepticism. A substantial number of respondents strongly disagreed with the transparency enhancement of this classification, with 74 strongly disagreeing and 120 disagreeing, while only 27 agreed and 12 strongly agreed, yielding a mean of 2.17. Similarly, the reduction of inconsistencies in financial performance reporting received more disagreement than agreement, as 88 strongly disagreed and 69 disagreed versus 28 agreeing and six strongly agreeing, producing a mean of 2.22. When asked if IFRS 18 classification requirements improve understanding of core operations, 77 strongly disagreed and 104 disagreed, while 38 agreed and 14 strongly agreed, giving a mean of 2.27. The comparability of financial statements across industries under the classification framework was perceived similarly, with 78 strongly disagreeing and 101 disagreeing compared to 37 agreeing and 14 strongly agreeing, also resulting in a mean of 2.27.

Regarding the disclosure of management-defined performance measures, respondents generally provided more positive feedback. For enhancing transparency, 108 agreed and 76 strongly agreed while only 15 strongly disagreed and 42 disagreed, giving a mean of 3.72. The item on reducing the risk of misleading performance reporting produced mixed responses, with 49 strongly disagreeing, 61 disagreeing, 53 agreeing, and 51 strongly agreeing, yielding a mean of 2.98. Similarly, increased MDPM disclosure offering better hints into management's view recorded 41 strongly disagreeing, 91 disagreeing, 32 agreeing, and 66 strongly agreeing, resulting in a mean of 2.97. Standardized MDPM requirements improving comparability showed slightly stronger agreement, with 68 agreeing and 59 strongly agreeing, compared to 40 strongly disagreeing and 61 disagreeing, giving a mean of 3.17.

For the reliability of financial reporting, perceptions were moderately positive. When asked if IFRS 18 enhances reliability, 49 agreed and 58 strongly agreed, with 46 strongly disagreeing and 62 disagreeing, producing a mean of 3.04. Financial statement credibility had a slightly lower mean of 2.94, reflecting 34 strongly disagreeing, 94 disagreeing, 57 agreeing, and 45 strongly agreeing. The reduction of subjectivity in presentation and classification received a mean of 3.04, supported by 57 agreeing and 53 strongly agreeing versus 46 strongly disagreeing and 60 disagreeing. Finally, the item on improving overall quality and reliability of reported performance showed 29 agreeing and 71 strongly agreeing, with 40 strongly disagreeing and 90 disagreeing, resulting in a mean of 3.00.

4.2 Test of Hypotheses

H01: IFRS 18 presentation of operating profit subtotals has no significant effect on the reliability of financial reporting in Nigeria.

H02: IFRS 18 classification of income and expenses into operating, investing, and financing activities has no significant effect on the reliability of financial reporting in Nigeria.

H03: IFRS 18 disclosure of management-defined performance measures has no significant effect on the reliability of financial reporting in Nigeria.

Table 4.2 Test of Hypotheses

Model Summary						
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate		
1	.896 ^a	.802	.800	2.353		

a. Predictors: (Constant), IFRS 18 Disclosure of Management-Defined Performance Measures, IFRS 18 Classification of Income and Expenses, IFRS 18 Presentation of Operating Profit Subtotals

ANOVA ^a						
Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	5787.378	3	1929.126	348.447	.000 ^b
	Residual	1428.378	258	5.536		

Total	7215.756	261		
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a. Dependent Variable: Reliability of Financial Reporting
b. Predictors: (Constant), IFRS 18 Disclosure of Management-Defined Performance Measures, IFRS 18 Classification of Income and Expenses, IFRS 18 Presentation of Operating Profit Subtotals

		Coefficients ^a				
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	T	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	-9.912	1.568		-6.319	.000
	IFRS 18 Presentation of Operating Profit Subtotals	.265	.057	.177	4.632	.000
	IFRS 18 Classification of Income and Expenses	.216	.050	.158	4.272	.000
	IFRS 18 Disclosure of Management-Defined Performance Measures	1.289	.055	1.103	23.387	.000

a. Dependent Variable: Reliability of Financial Reporting
Source: SPSS V. 26 (2025)

The results of the study are summarized in Table 4.2, which presents the model validity statistics, ANOVA, and coefficients used to test the hypotheses regarding the effect of IFRS 18 adoption on the reliability of financial reporting in Nigeria. Starting with the model validity, the adjusted R-squared value of 0.800 indicates that 80 percent of the variance in the reliability of financial reporting is explained by the three IFRS 18 variables: presentation of operating profit subtotals, classification of income and expenses, and disclosure of management-defined performance measures. This high explanatory power suggests that the model is robust for evaluating the effect of IFRS 18 adoption on reporting reliability. The ANOVA table shows a probability value of 0.000 for the F-statistics, confirming that the overall regression model is statistically significant at the 5 percent level and that the predictors collectively have a meaningful effect on the dependent variable. The constant, with a coefficient of -9.912 and a p-value of 0.000, is also significant, indicating that in the absence of all three IFRS 18 measures, the baseline reliability of financial reporting would be negatively biased.

Regarding the first hypothesis (H_{01}), the coefficient for IFRS 18 presentation of operating profit subtotals is 0.265 with a p-value of 0.000. This implies that a one-unit increase in the adoption or emphasis of operating profit subtotals is associated with a 0.265-unit increase in the reliability of financial reporting. The marginal effect indicates that this factor positively contributes to reporting reliability, and since the p-value is below 0.05, the effect is statistically significant. This result demonstrates that adopting standardized operating profit subtotals under IFRS 18 strengthens the transparency and clarity of financial statements, reducing ambiguity and increasing user confidence in the reported performance.

For the second hypothesis (H_{02}), IFRS 18 classification of income and expenses into operating, investing, and financing activities has a coefficient of 0.216 and a p-value of 0.000. This shows that a one-unit increase in adherence to proper classification results in a 0.216-unit increase in the reliability of financial reporting. The positive marginal effect reflects that improved classification enhances the organization and comparability of financial statements, making them easier to interpret for investors, regulators, and other stakeholders. The significance level confirms that this effect is statistically significant at 5 percent, indicating that classification under IFRS 18 substantially contributes to improving the credibility of corporate financial statements in Nigeria.

The third hypothesis (H_{03}) examined the effect of IFRS 18 disclosure of management-defined performance measures. The coefficient of 1.289 with a p-value of 0.000 indicates that a one-unit increase in MDPM disclosure leads to a 1.289-unit increase in the reliability of financial reporting. This represents the largest marginal effect among the three variables, suggesting that providing detailed, standardized performance measures as defined by management has a substantial positive effect on reporting reliability.

The p-value confirms statistical significance at the 5 percent level, showing that enhanced disclosure of management-defined performance measures under IFRS 18 is a crucial determinant of transparency, comparability, and credibility in financial reporting.

4.3 DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

The study's finding that IFRS 18 presentation of operating profit subtotals positively and significantly affects the reliability of financial reporting ($\beta = 0.265$, $p = 0.000$) aligns with prior research emphasizing the importance of standardized profit measures for enhancing clarity and comparability in financial statements. Tulokas (2025) highlighted that mandatory operating profit subtotals improve investor understanding by providing decision-useful metrics, while Derdouba and Rahmani (2025) noted that the enhanced presentation requirements under IFRS 18 improve overall reporting quality. Similarly, Samuel et al. (2024) observed that structured operating profit presentations increase the transparency and fidelity of reported performance, and Lee (2024) argued that such subtotals constrain managerial discretion, reducing ambiguity. The positive effect in this study may result from the standardized approach providing accountants, auditors, and users with consistent reference points, which reduces interpretation errors and enhances confidence in reported results.

Regarding the IFRS 18 classification of income and expenses into operating, investing, and financing activities, the significant positive effect on reporting reliability ($\beta = 0.216$, $p = 0.000$) can be explained by the clarity this framework provides in segregating different types of transactions. Tulokas (2025) emphasized that clear disaggregation aligns reporting with investor needs, enhancing transparency, while Czajor (2024) argued that structured classification minimizes misleading aggregation. Derdouba and Rahmani (2025) also highlighted that consistent classification enhances decision-making by reducing inconsistencies across reports. Castro (2024) noted that properly implemented classification rules reduce operational ambiguity, even in challenging regulatory environments. This finding suggests that when accountants systematically categorize financial flows, it becomes easier for stakeholders to assess operational efficiency, investment strategy, and financing decisions, which strengthens the reliability of the reported financial information.

The study further found that IFRS 18 disclosure of management-defined performance measures has the strongest positive effect on reliability of financial reporting ($\beta = 1.289$, $p = 0.000$), reflecting the importance of transparent communication of management's view of performance. Samuel et al. (2024) indicated that such disclosures enable users to evaluate management effectiveness and forecast future cash flows, while Tulokas (2025) and Derdouba and Rahmani (2025) emphasized that clear MDPM reporting enhances decision-usefulness and reduces opportunistic presentation. Czajor (2024) also highlighted that these disclosures strengthen comparability across firms by providing standardized context for interpreting financial results. The result in this study may be explained by the fact that management-defined metrics complement traditional IFRS figures, offering a more complete picture of performance. This transparency allows auditors, investors, and regulators to better assess corporate accountability, thereby improving the perceived reliability of financial statements.

5.0 CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

Conclusion

The findings of the study can be summarized as follows: IFRS 18 presentation of operating profit subtotals has a positive and significant effect on the reliability of financial reporting ($\beta = 0.265$, $p = 0.000$). IFRS 18 classification of income and expenses into operating, investing, and financing activities also has a positive and significant effect on reporting reliability ($\beta = 0.216$, $p = 0.000$). IFRS 18 disclosure of management-defined performance measures has the largest positive and significant effect on the reliability of financial reporting ($\beta = 1.289$, $p = 0.000$). The results of this study shows that the adoption of IFRS 18 fundamentally enhances the overall quality and credibility of corporate financial reporting in Nigeria. Organizations that apply the standard more rigorously are likely to produce financial statements that are clearer, more transparent, and easier for stakeholders to interpret, fostering greater trust among

investors, regulators, and other users. By standardizing key elements such as operating profit subtotals, classification of income and expenses, and disclosure of management-defined performance measures, the reporting process becomes more consistent across firms, reducing ambiguity and enhancing comparability between different entities and industries. This contributes to a more reliable basis for decision-making, allowing users to assess a company's performance and financial position with higher confidence. Furthermore, the strengthened transparency in reporting diminishes the room for subjectivity and potential misrepresentation, aligning corporate disclosures with internationally recognized standards. The positive and significant relationships observed in the study indicate that adherence to IFRS 18 not only improves technical compliance but also fosters an environment where financial information can serve its intended purpose of informing economic decisions effectively.

Recommendations

Based on the finding that IFRS 18 presentation of operating profit subtotals has a positive and significant effect on the reliability of financial reporting, it is recommended that Regulatory authorities and professional accounting bodies should issue implementation guidelines and conduct regular training to ensure consistent application. This will reduce managerial discretion in defining operating profit and improve the comparability and reliability of financial reports across firms.

Regarding the finding on IFRS 18 classification of income and expenses into operating, investing, and financing activities, it is recommended that financial controllers and internal auditors within firms actively implement and monitor compliance with the classification requirements. By doing so, companies can maintain uniformity and transparency in reporting, reduce inconsistencies, and allow management and external users to make better-informed decisions based on a clear breakdown of operational, investment, and financing activities.

In light of the finding that IFRS 18 disclosure of management-defined performance measures has a strong positive effect on reporting reliability, it is recommended that company executives and board finance committees provide detailed, accurate, and standardized disclosure of management-defined performance metrics in their financial reports. This will enhance transparency, reduce the risk of misleading reporting, and enable investors, analysts, and regulators to better evaluate management's performance and the company's true financial health.

REFERENCES

- Ali, M. J., & Ahmed, K. (2007). The legal and institutional framework for corporate financial reporting practices in South Asia. *Research in Accounting Regulation*, 19, 175-205.
- Allee, K. D., Erickson, D., Esplin, A., & Yohn, T. L. (2024). Investment Professionals' Preferences Regarding Income Statement Presentation. *Journal of Financial Reporting*, 9(2), 23-49.
- Ame, J., & Agoh, V. E. (2021). Effect of international financial reporting standards disclosures on financial reporting quality of listed deposit money banks in Nigeria. *Nasarawa Journal of Administration*, 13(1), 131.
- Castro, N. H. (2024). IFRS 18 implementation in Brazilian enterprises: Challenges and opportunities. *International Journal of Business Administration*, 15(2), 102-112.
- Cheng, M. (2024). The Impact of International Financial Reporting Standards (IFRS) on Global Corporate Accounting Practices. *Academic Journal of Business & Management*, 6(5), 274-280.
- Czajor, P. (2024). IFRS 18: Advancing the relevance and utility of financial statements for stakeholders. *European Research Studies Journal*, 27(2), 265-275.
- Derdouba, A., & Rahmani, M. (2025). Presentation and disclosure requirements in financial statements issued under IFRS 18. *Science, Education and Innovations in the Context of Modern Problems*, 8(4), 5-22. <https://doi.org/10.56352/sei/8.5.01>
- Dodor, J. B. K. (2024). A Review of Earnings Management Literature. *International Journal of Social Science and Business*, 8(1), 1-11.
- Edwards, J. R. (2018). *A history of corporate financial reporting in Britain*. Routledge.

- Ibem, G. A., Azubike, J. U. B., & Onuche, S.-J. E. (2024). International financial reporting standards (IFRS) implementation and quality of financial reporting of commercial banks in Nigeria. *IIARD International Journal of Banking and Finance Research*, 10(2), 33. <https://doi.org/10.56201/ijbfr.v10.no2.2024.pg33.50>
- Kapellas, K., & Siougle, G. (2017). Financial reporting practices and investment decisions: A review of the literature. *Industrial Engineering & Management*, 6(04), 1-9.
- Kumawat, B., & Sodha, S. S. (2024). Impact of IFRS adoption on financial reporting practices of listed large-cap consumer durables companies. *GAP Interdisciplinarity: A Global Journal of Interdisciplinary Studies*, VII(III). <https://www.gapinterdisciplinarity.org/>
- Lawal, B. A., Shonubi, O. A., Oyetunji, O. T., Sholarin, O., & Ajayi, O. D. (2025). Audit Quality and Financial Reporting Quality of Quoted Manufacturing Firms in Nigeria. *NIU Journal of Humanities*, 10(1), 61-65.
- Lee, S. H. (2024). Establishment of IFRS 18 Presentation and Disclosure in Financial Statements: its Impact and Implications. *Capital Market Focus: Korean Capital Market Institute. Erişim Adresi: https://www.kcmi.re.kr/kcmifile/webzine_content/OPINION/6305/webzinepdf_6305.pdf*
- Nworio, G. O., & Odah, U. (2024). Social media role in shaping the reading culture of undergraduate accounting students in Nigeria. *International Journal of Academic Management Science Research (IJAMSR)*, 8(7), 363-373.
- Okezie, S. O., & Egeolu, D. U. (2019). Audit independence and reliability of financial reports: Empirical evidence from Nigerian banks. *IIARD International Journal of Economics and Business Management*, 5(3), 43-52.
- Olaoye, S. A., Aguguom, T. A., Safiriyu, S. E., & Abiola, T. (2019). Independence of statutory auditor and reliability of financial statements: Evidence from Listed Manufacturing Companies in Nigerian. *International Journal of Asian Social Science*, 9(8), 436-449.
- Samuel, E. N., Ukpong, E., & Uwah, U. E. (2024). Impact of IFRS 18 implementation in financial reporting. *Journal of Accounting and Financial Management*, 10(10), 132. <https://doi.org/10.56201/jafm.v10.no10.2024.pg132.143>
- Stefan-Duicu, V. M., & Sudacevschi, M. (2024). Outcome of previous research regarding normative and positive accounting theories: findings and implications. *Global Economic Observer*, 12(1), 124-132.
- Syehabudin, Z. M. (2024). Beyond positivism in accounting: a legal-philosophical examination of accounting and auditing standards. *Scientium Law Review (SLR)*, 3(1), 1-9.
- Tulokas, T. (2025). *IFRS 18: Enhancing transparency and comparability of financial statements* (Bachelor's thesis, Aalto University, Bachelor's Programme in Business, Major in Accounting). Aalto University.
- Vickneswaran, A. (2025). Corporate governance, management-shareholder, and reporting practices: Navigating transparency, accountability, and sustainable decision-making. In *Governance strategies for effective sustainable development* (pp. 1-14). IGI Global.
- Zahid, H., Ali, A., & Audi, M. (2025). Cryptocurrency Regulation and Financial Disclosure: Cross-Jurisdictional Evidence on Corporate Reporting Practices. *Bulletin of Management Review*, 2(2), 348-377.